

WHAT IS A LESSON PLANNING?

Karimova Shakhloza Boykuzi kizi

FSU, teacher of English Language department

Nasimov Jaloldin Soyibjon o'g'li

Master's degree student, FSU

DARSNI REJALASHTIRISH NIMA?

Karimova Shaxloza Boyquzi qizi

FDU, Ingliz tili fakulteti o'qituvchisi

Nasimov Jaloldin Soyibjon o'g'li

FDU Lingvistika: ingliz tili 2 kurs magistranti

ЧТО ТАКОЕ ПЛАНИРОВАНИЕ УРОКА?

Каримова Шахлоза Бойкузи кизи

ФГУ, преподаватель кафедры Английского языка

Насимов Жалолдин Соибжон угли

студент 2 курса магистратуры Лингвистики английского языка ФГУ

Abstract. This article gives information about a lesson plan and strategies on lesson planning. There are given a number of special features of a lesson plan and stages of a lesson plan so as to make a lesson much more effective. Besides that, article describes six main aspects of a lesson plan, such as lesson objectives, related requirements, lesson materials, lesson procedure, assessment method, lesson reflection.

Key words: lesson, lesson plan, objective, assessment, learning process, classroom management, lesson objectives, related requirements, lesson materials, lesson procedure, assessment method, lesson reflection.

Аннотация. В данной статье содержится информация о плане урока и стратегиях планирования урока. Дан ряд особенностей плана урока и этапов плана урока, чтобы сделать урок более эффективным. Кроме того, в статье описываются шесть основных аспектов плана урока, такие как цели урока, соответствующие требования, материалы урока, процедура урока, метод оценивания, рефлексия урока.

Ключевые слова: урок, план урока, цель, оценка, учебный процесс, управление классом, цели урока, сопутствующие требования, материалы урока, процедура урока, метод оценивания, рефлексия урока.

A lesson plan is the instructor's road map of what students need to learn and how it will be done effectively during the class time. Then, teachers can design appropriate learning activities and develop strategies to obtain feedback on student learning. A successful lesson plan addresses and integrates these three key components:

- Objectives for student learning
- Teaching/learning activities
- Strategies to check student understanding

The first step is to determine what you want students to learn and be able to do at the end of class. To help you specify your objectives for student learning, answer the following questions:

What is the topic of the lesson?

What do I want students to learn?

What do I want them to understand and be able to do at the end of class?

What do I want them to take away from this particular lesson?

Lesson plan is teacher's daily guide for what students need to learn, how it will be taught, and how learning will be measured. Lesson plans help teachers be more effective in the classroom by providing a detailed outline to follow each class period. We are going to illustrate the most effective parts or aspects of a lesson plan in the following figure.

Figure 1. **The most effective lesson plans have six key parts**

1. Lesson objectives list what students will be able to do after completing the lesson. In the context of lesson planning, you can use the SMART criteria to determine your lesson objectives:

- Is the objective **specific**?
- Is the objective **measurable**?
- Is the objective **attainable** by all students?

- Is the objective **relevant** to your class and students?
- Is the objective **time-based** to align with your syllabus?

2. Related requirements are *national, state, or school standards* that dictate what you need to teach in a class.

3. List of materials that we need to teach the lesson and measure student outcomes. Common types of lesson materials include:

- Student handouts
- [Textbooks](#)
- Visual aids
- Grading rubrics
- Activity packets
- Computers / Tablets

The list of materials for each lesson depends on what you plan to teach, how you'll teach it, and how you'll measure lesson objectives. Because of this, many teachers compile their list of lesson materials in tandem with their lesson procedure.

4. Lesson procedure is an in-depth explanation of how the lesson will progress in the classroom. The lesson procedure is essentially step-by-step instructions that walk you through everything from the time students enter the classroom until the bell rings at the end of the period.

It's smart to be very detailed in this portion of your lesson plan. When writing your lesson procedure, you need to choose the type of activities that will help students meet the lesson objectives. To do that, you can answer a list of questions, including:

- How will you introduce the topic?
- What's the best way to teach this information to your students?
- How can you incorporate problem solving and critical thinking?
- What real-life scenarios relate to this topic?
- Does this topic lend itself to group work?

It's also a great idea to find out how other teachers address the topics in the classroom. You can do this by talking to coworkers, joining an online community, or searching for lesson ideas on educational blogs.

5. Assessment method measures whether your students learned a lesson's information and met your lesson objectives. The methods listed on your lesson plan will most often be formative assessments and vary from lesson to lesson.

To start, there are dozens of ways to measure student learning through formative assessments. Some of the most common assessment options include:

- Quizzes
- Hands-on activities
- Writing assignments
- Group presentations

- Exit slips
- Class journal entries

In addition, your assessment method may be an in-class assignment or homework for students to complete prior to the next class.

When choosing your assessment method, it's important to incorporate your lesson objectives. If an objective was related to understanding a concept, consider an assessment that requires students to explain that concept. If an objective was for students to demonstrate a skill, design an assessment to confirm they can do that skill. Also, while many assessments receive grades in a class, formative assessments do not always need to be graded.

Ultimately, the purpose of this assessment is to measure how well your students learned a lesson's material based on the way you presented information. This measurement will help you wrap up each lesson plan with the lesson reflection.

6. Lesson reflection portion of a lesson plan encourages teachers to take notes on how to improve a lesson after it has been completed.

By this point, your lesson has clear objectives, a plan for teaching, and a way to assess student learning. But if you do not critically consider whether you succeeded, you are doing a disservice to your future students.

When completing your lesson reflection, ask yourself questions like:

- Did a part of the lesson take longer than expected?
- Was there a portion that students asked for a lot of help with?
- Did students breeze through the information with no problem?
- Were students engaged and interested in the lesson?
- Were the objectives met by most (or all) of the students?

Furthermore, there is another main peculiarity of a lesson plan which is called timeline/time management. There are a number of features teachers should focus on:

- Estimate how much time each of the activities will take, then plan some extra time for each;
- When you prepare your lesson plan, next to each activity indicate how much time you expect it will take;
- Plan a few minutes at the end of class to answer any remaining questions and to sum up key points;
- Plan an extra activity or discussion question in case you have time left;
- Be flexible – be ready to adjust your lesson plan to students' needs and focus on what seems to be more productive rather than sticking to your original plan.

To conclude, letting your students know what they will be learning and doing in class will help keep them more engaged and on track. Providing a meaningful organization of the class time can help students not only remember better, but also follow your presentation and understand the rationale behind the planned learning

activities. Take a few minutes after each class to reflect on what worked well and why, and what you could have done differently. Identifying successful and less successful organization of class time and activities would make it easier to adjust to the contingencies of the classroom. If needed, revise the lesson plan once more.

Reference:

1. Ambrose, S., Bridges, M., Lovett, M., DiPietro, M., & Norman, M. (2010). *How learning works: 7 research-based principles for smart teaching*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey Bass.
2. EDUCAUSE (2005). Potential Learning Activities. Retrieved April 7 2017, from EDUCAUSE
3. Karimova, S. (2022). IMPLEMENTATION OF INQUIRY-BASED LEARNING FOR TEACHING ENGLISH. *Scientific progress*, 3(3), 820-826.
4. Iskandarova, S., Karimova, S., & Abdugarimova, M. (2021). NEGATIVE PREFIXES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *Збірник наукових праць SCIENTIA*.
5. Karimova, S. B. (2022). BELIEFS ABOUT TEACHING GRAMMAR. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, 2(Special Issue 2), 123-127.
6. Bakhridinovna, B. S. (2022, December). STUDY OF ECONOMIC TERMS IN ENGLISH CLASSES. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 1, No. 9, pp. 40-44).
7. Bakhridinovna, B. S. (2022). PROBLEMS OF ALTERNATIVE CHOICE OF SEVERAL METHODS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 76-79.
8. Bahridinovna, B. S. (2022). MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH LESSONS. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(3), 316-319.
9. Бобокулова, Ш. Б. (2021, November). Использование Интегрированных Навыков В Обучении Английскому Языку. In " *ONLINE-CONFERENCE*" PLATFORM (pp. 120-125).
10. Bakhridinovna, B. S. (2021). Ways of developing communicative skills in the language environment of a foreign language lesson. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(11), 57-65.
11. Gafurova, S. S., & Yusuphadjaeva, S. T. (2023). ANXIETY-PHOBIC DISORDERS IN IRRITABLE BOWEL SYNDROME AND THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PSYCHOTHERAPY AND PSYCHOPHARMACOTHERAPY. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(1), 110-115.

12. Nazira, K., Siddikovna, T. G., Davranovna, D. A., Takhirovich, D. A., & Tulkinovich, O. S. (2021). Cardiovascular complications in patients who have had covid on the background of diabetes mellitus 2. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 2(3), 37-41.

13. Гафурова, С. Ш., & Юсупходжаева, С. Т. (2022). ТРЕВОЖНЫЕ-ФОБИЧЕСКИЕ РАССТРОЙСТВА ПРИ СИНДРОМЕ РАЗДРАЖЕННОГО КИШЕЧНИКА И ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ПСИХОТЕРАПИИ И ПСИХОФАРМАКОТЕРАПИИ.

14. Юсупходжаева, С. Т. (2020). ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ БОЛЬНЫХ РЕВМАТОИДНЫМ АРТРИТОМ И МЕТОДЫ ИХ ПСИХОКОРРЕКЦИИ. In *Global Science and Innovations 2020* (pp. 170-174).

15. Юсупходжаева, С. Т. (2020). Психоэмоциональнке расстройства при ревматоидном артрите и методы их психокоррекции. *Журн. Неврология*, (3).

16. Yusuphodjaeva, S. T., & Gafurova, S. S. (2023). METHODS OF COGNITIVE-BEHAVIORAL PSYCHOTHERAPY IN THE TREATMENT OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(1-2), 701-706.

17. Djuraeva, Z. A., Togaeva, G. S., & Davranova, A. D. (2022). Knowledge and Attitude towards Psychiatry among Nursing Staffs in Tertiary Health Care Hospital. *Advances in Clinical Medical Research*, 3(2), 4-6.

18. Shukhratovna, N. G., Siddiqovna, T. G., Davranovna, D. A., & Nodirovna, A. S. (2022). Analysis of the thyroid status of pregnant women in the iodine-deficient region. *The American Journal of Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Research*, 4(01), 74-78.

19. Karimova, N. A. (2020). Davranova AD Bakhronov SD Features of the pathology of the reproductive system in girls in the iododicitis region. *Re-health. Andijon*, (4), 112-114.